
GC-MS Analysis of Six Bioactive Compounds Isolated From The Ethanol Leaf Extract of *Andrographis paniculata* (Acanthaceae)

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Abstract Medicinal plants offer infinite source of useful therapeutics. They offer promise for the treatment of human disease. Today we are still in need of safer, cheaper and effective drug products. The present study was carried out to characterize the bioactive substances present in *Andrographis paniculata* (Acanthaceae) by GC-MS analysis. *Andrographis paniculata* is a medicinal plant used traditionally in Nigeria to treat boils, diarrhea, dysentery and malaria. The phytochemical screening revealed that the extract contains alkaloid, steroidal glycoside, terpene, carbohydrate, anthraquinone, polyphenol, saponin, tannin, resins, protein, coumarine, amino acid and anthracyanoside. The column chromatography of the extract yielded 78 eluates (A1-A78). Eluates A₂₈, A₂₉ (R_f = 0.48), A₃₁, A₃₂ (R_f = 0.23) and A₃₆, A₃₈, A₃₉ (R_f = 0.49) yielded white crystals. The GC-MS of the crystals gave rise to six chemical compounds (isolates 1-6). These compounds may be responsible for various pharmacological actions.

Keywords *Andrographis paniculata*, ethanol, bioactive compounds.

Introduction

Natural products have been a major source of new drugs [1]. The continuous and perpetual people's interest in medicinal plants has brought about today's modern and sophisticated fashion of their processing and usage [2]. Medicinal plants are defined as plants which contain substances that can be used for the therapeutic purpose in one or more of its organs or substances which are precursors for the synthesis of useful drugs [3].

Andrographis paniculata

Native populations of *Andrographis paniculata* are spread throughout India, Java, Malaysia, Indonesia, Hong Kong, Thailand and Singapore. In Nigeria, *Andrographis paniculata* is used for the treatment of diarrhoea, dysentery, cough, sores, snake bites and malaria [4].

Material and Methods

Column and Thin Layer Chromatography

500g of the dried plant material was macerated with 70% ethanol. Phytochemical screening of the plant was carried out using standard methods [5].

An open glass column was used for this chromatographic analysis. The column was packed with silica gel 60-120 mesh. The silica gel was made up into slurry with benzene. The slurry was poured into a glass column followed by the powdered ethanol extract of the plant. 78 eluates (A1-A78) were obtained using different solvent systems.

The solvent system for thin layer chromatography was benzene-ethylacetate (6:4). The spots on the TLC plates were detected using UV-light (wavelength 254nm). The chromatographic separation of ethanol extract gave 78 eluates

(A1-A78). Some eluates produced single spots each. Fractions with similar retention factors (R_f) were pooled together. These fractions yielded white needle-like crystals. The crystals were sent for spectroscopic analysis (GC-MS).

GC-MS Analysis

The hyphenated technique of gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrophotometer (GC-MS), shimadzu, Japan was employed to obtain the chromatogram. The experiment was performed at a Colum oven temperature at 250 °C at a pressure of 100.2 kpa with a total flow rate of 6.2 ml/minute. The infrared spectra were recorded on Fourier Transform Infrared spectrophotometer, model 8400s, shimadz, Japan.

Identification of Bioactive Compounds

Interpretation of mass spectrum was carried out using the data base of National Institute of Standard Technology (NIST Version 21), WILEY and FAME. The unknown compounds found in the plant extract were matched with the spectrum of the known compounds stored in NIST, WILEY and FAME, the MS Library and predicted from Dukes' Ethno Botanical Data base.

Results and Discussion

GC-MS chromatograph of the ethanol extract of *Andrographis paniculata* yielded 6 chemical compounds. On comparison of the mass spectra of the comounds with the NIST Library the six compounds were characterized and identified .

Table 1: Activity of Compounds Identified in the Ethanol Extract of *Andrographis Paniculata*:

S/N	Name of Compound	MF	MWT	Class	Activity
1	6, 10-Dimethyl undecanone	$C_{13}H_{26}O$	198	Ketone	Flavor, Fragrance
2	3-pentadecyl phenol	$C_{21}H_{36}O$	304	Alcohol	Antidiareal
3	1-methyl-4-/2-pentenyl-oxy-benzene	$C_{12}H_{16}O$	176	Alkene	Antimicrobial
4	Bicyclo-hex-3-en-one	$C_{10}H_{14}O$	150	Ketone	perfumery
5	Para-methyl phenyl acetate	$C_9H_{10}O_2$	150	Ester	Surfactant
6	4-phenylbut-3-en-1-yne	$C_{10}H_8$	128	alkyne	Antiasthmatics bronchodihators

Fragmentation pattern of isolated compounds

Isolate 1

Base Peak is 43 at 100%, Molecular ion (M^+) is 198 and molecular formula, $C_{13}H_{26}O$.

M/Z, Relative Intensity (%), Interpretation is shown below.

41 (25%) M-157 ($C_{10}H_{21}O$), 43 (100%) M-155 ($C_{10}H_{19}O$), 58 (95%) M-140 ($C_9H_{16}O$), 71 (30%) M-127 ($C_8H_{15}O$), 85 (15%) M-133 ($C_7H_{13}O$), 109 (10%) M-89 (C_6HO), 180 (10%) M-18 (H_2O), 198 (2%) M^+ .

Isolate 2

Base Peak is 108 at 100%, Molecular ion (M^+) is 304 and molecular formula, $C_{21}H_{36}O$.

M/Z, Relative Intensity(%) and Interpretation is as follows

57 (10%) M-247 ($C_{18}H_{26}$), 77 (10%) M-227 ($C_{16}H_{19}O$), 91 (5%) M-213 ($C_{14}H_{29}O$), 108 (100%) M-196 ($C_{14}H_{12}O$), 121 (10%) M-183 ($C_{12}H_{23}O$), 133 (2%) M-171 ($C_{11}H_{23}O$), 149 (2%) M-155 ($C_{10}H_{19}O$), 304 (2%) M^+ .

Isolate 3

Base Peak is 108 at 100%, Molecular ion (M^+) is 176 and molecular formular, $C_{21}H_{36}O$.

M/Z, Relative Intensity(%) and the Interpretation is below.

38 (10%) M-138 ($C_9H_{14}O$), 41 (30%) M-135 ($C_9H_{11}O$), 53 (5%) M-123 ($C_8H_{11}O$), 69 (5%) M-107 (C_7H_7O), 77 (15%) M-99 ($C_6H_{11}O$), 91 (5%) M-85 (C_5H_9O), 108 (100%) M-68 (C_4H_4O), 176 (5%) M^+ .

Isolate 4

Base Peak is 108 at 100%, Molecular ion (M^+) 150 and molecular formula, $C_{10}H_{14}O$

M/Z, Relative Intensity(%), Interpretation

43 (10%) M-107 (C_7H_7O), 67 (10%) M-83 (C_5H_7O), 79 (20%) M-71 (C_4H_7O), 91 (50%) M-59 (C_4H_7O), 108 (100%) M-42 (C_2H_2O), 122 (10%) M-28 (CO)
135 (20%) M-15 (CH_3), 150 (20%) M^+

Isolate 5

Base Peak is 108 at 100%, Molecular ion (M^+) and 150 and molecular Formula, $C_9H_{10}O_2$

M/Z, Relative Intensity (%) and Interpretation is shown below.

41 (2%) M-109 (C₇H₉O), 43 (35%) M-107 (C₆H₃O), 63 (2%) M-87 (C₄H₇O₂), 77 (25%) M-73 (C₃H₅O₂), 90 (2%) M-60 (C₂H₂O₂), 108 (100%) M-42 (C₂H₂O)
120 (2%) M-30 (CH₂O), 150 (15%) M⁺

Isolate 6

Base Peak is 128 at 100%, Molecular ion (M⁺) is 128 and molecular Formula, C₁₀H₈.

M/Z, Relative Intensity(%) and Interpretation is given below.

39 (10%) M-89 (C₇H₅), 51 (35%) M-77 (C₆H₅), 63 (20%) M-65 (C₃H₅)
77 (10%) M-51 (C₄H₃), 87 (2%) M-41 (C₃H₅), 102 (15%) M-26 (C₂H₂)
128 (100%) M⁺

Structures of chemical compounds isolated from *andrographis paniculata*

Compound 1

6,10-dimethyl-2-undecanone

Compounds 2

3-pentadecylphenol

Compound 3

1-methyl-4-(pentyloxy)benzene

Compound 4

Compound 5

1-isopropyl-4-methylbicyclo[3.1.0]hex-3-en-2-one

Compound 6

1-(but-1-en-3-ynyl)benzene

Discussion

Researchers have focused on pharmacologically active compounds from natural sources. GC-MS is used to identification the constituents of volatile matter, long chain and branched chain hydrocarbons, alcohols, acids ketones and esters. 6, 10-Dimethylundecanone and Bicyclo-hex-3-en-one are ketone bodies. These compounds have been reportedly used in making flavors, fragrance, perfume and Antioxidants [6]. The Antidiarrheal property of 3-pentadecyl phenol has been reported [7]. 1-methyl-4-[2-pentenyl-oxy-benzene is said to have antimicrobial activity [8] while paramethyl phenyl cetate is a surfactant [9] 4-phenylbut-3-en-yne is antiagthmatic and bronchodilator [10-12].

Conclusion

The findings of this study led to the following conclusion:

1. The phytochemical screening revealed that the extract contain alkaloid, steroidal glycoside, terpenes, carbohydrate, anthraquinone, polyphenol, saponin, tannin, resins protein, coumarine, amino acid and anthracyanoside.
2. The secondary metabolites and the isolated compounds are responsible for the pharmacological actions of the plant.

Recommendations

The crystals obtained from chromatographic study should be tested for their antiplasmodial activity because the plant is used traditionally in Nigeria to treat malaria.

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